

Human flourishing versus burnout syndrome in the university context: The case of Club 1943 - Karaoke at Tec de Monterrey

Gerardo Salvador González Lara¹, María Eugenia Morales Hinojosa², Manuel Cebral Loureda³, Raúl Carlos Verduzco Garza⁴

¹ Department of Humanistic Studies, School of Humanities and Education, Campus Monterrey, Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico

² Institutional Event Management Center, Campus Monterrey, Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico

³ Department of Humanistic Studies, School of Humanities and Education, Campus Monterrey, Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico

⁴ Associate Director of Department of Humanistic Studies, School of Humanities and Education, Campus Monterrey, Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico

Email: gsgonzal@tec.mx , emorales@tec.mx , manuel.cebral@tec.mx , raul.verduzco@tec.mx

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15847251>

Abstract

The vocation of most engineering and science professors is admirable; however, designing educational models appropriate for today's students becomes a challenge that requires ongoing training and work in multiple aspects of teaching. This demand is a significant source of burnout syndrome, which is reflected in stress, physical and mental exhaustion, decreased academic productivity and intellectual vitality, and demotivation, among other symptoms. In December 2015, professors spontaneously selected a recreational and social space on campus with a novel element: karaoke; this element contributed to creating a sense of shared joy and freedom. This karaoke session took root naturally and was named Club 1943 Karaoke. It is currently held monthly and is attended by an average of 130 professors per session. This cultural phenomenon in the university setting is worthy of analysis as an element of cohesion and well-being for the faculty community. We started from the research assumption: "The karaoke at Club 1943 [on the Monterrey Campus of Tecnológico de Monterrey] is a cultural instrument that fulfills a necessary function in preventing, avoiding, and reducing the incidence of burnout syndrome in the academic community, and in promoting human flourishing in its professors." This research assumption was demonstrated using quantitative and qualitative indicators, and it was concluded that karaoke is a collective response of faculty to burnout syndrome and a trigger for their human flourishing. Based on the results, the institution decided to formally incorporate it into its economic budget as an investment and integrated it into the services it offers to its academic community by organizing it monthly. The institution conceptualized it as a model of coexistence and recreation to combat burnout syndrome and an opportunity to enhance human flourishing in professors. It can be replicated at other universities, and this research offers some recommendations for its implementation.

Keywords: Human flourishing, burnout, culture, karaoke.

1. Introduction

Following the social, political, and economic impact of the Industrial Revolution in Europe, and later in America and the rest of the world, groups or guilds of people emerged that identified themselves as social collectives engaged in work-related activity within the modern economic structure. Their identity represented, within the collective, unity, problems, challenges, and common interests, and externally, allowed them to express themselves as an active group within the machinery of industrialization. Thus, these forms of organization based on work life became fundamental spaces of socialization for millions of people, for their survival and that of their families. It is suggestive to remember the film *Modern Times* (Dir. Charles Chaplin / USA / 1936 / 83 min) as an example of this unionization process: "...it is a film that follows the life of a factory worker, who is affected by the frenetic pace of assembly line production, which ultimately leads him to lose his sanity. After a series of unfortunate incidents, he is imprisoned but escapes by chance. Once free, he finds himself struggling to survive in an increasingly modern industrial society." (Cultura/UNAM, 2023)

Thus, throughout the 20th century, labor collectives were formed by very different activities or groups of workers, who were inserted into the economically active population. Thus, industries of employees and

professionals focused on common economic and labor activity were globally formed, as is the case in the construction industry, the automotive industry, and the entertainment industry, to name just a few. In the academic context, the teaching staff constitutes a guild or collective like those described above, namely, groups of people with specialized training in their area of academic knowledge, with experience and knowledge in teaching/learning didactics, as well as for the development of competencies.

University professors are a group or professional collective with similar problems, concerns, challenges, and interests, with a very clear collective identity. Like all other professions, they face the conditions of the 21st century that particularly affect educational work. These factors include technological advances in general, information technologies, artificial intelligence, consumer habits, and other factors that impact current university culture.

It should be noted that, although the main theme of this conference focuses on identifying and sharing innovative teaching methods to connect professional development and active learning in students of various engineering disciplines, the main promoter of this project is the professor. Professors are the guides of this training, and their physical and emotional well-being are essential for their performance in front of students. Their human flourishing is considered a relevant factor that is present simultaneously and integrated into the teaching process for active learning, with a direct impact on the teaching process. Healthy, happy, harmonious, and enthusiastic professors inspire greater enthusiasm for the subject they teach and greater student engagement. A professor whose teaching work is integrated with their human flourishing achieves a communication and information process that is closer to students, further enhancing their intellectual curiosity and desire to learn.

As evidence of the presence of burnout syndrome in the current work environment, and especially in the work context of university professors, researchers have shared indicators of tiredness and exhaustion, and their impact on professors from different parts of the world, considering this data representative of the profession. According to Torres (2025), in Mexico alone, "75% of Mexicans suffer from fatigue due to work-related stress, according to data from the Mexican Social Security Institute (IMSS)." Amezcua (in Torres 2025) states that "professors are not exempt from suffering the consequences of this condition... *Being a professor is classified as one of the professions with the highest psychosocial risks such as burnout*" stated at the 2023 National Meeting of Professors of the Tecnológico de Monterrey. Garcia (2022) states that: "For organizations, burnout syndrome has negative consequences such as low productivity, absenteeism due to disability, resignations, an increase in accidents due to lack of concentration, and sometimes legal issues." Lozano Luviano (UNAM 2022) among the ways to deal with it suggests "support in decision-making, organization of work and personal time, and management of relationships in search of a better quality of life" and proposes that institutions should consider the resources invested in the face of Burnout syndrome as an investment in the health of their collaborators and/or as an expense.

Delgado (2019) states that "Institutions focus on the socio-emotional well-being of students, but who is taking care of that of educators?" since according to a study by the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation and the Pennsylvania State University (Penn State), "teaching is one of the most stressful professions in the United States. The stress suffered by teaching professionals affects their health, commitment, performance, and satisfaction, making it one of the professions with the highest turnover in history." 46% of professors report feeling stressed daily during the school year (in Delgado 2019). This is why she states that "educators also need support to manage their stress." A study by the Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte on sleep habits reported that "46% of high school professors were diagnosed with excessive daytime sleepiness. In addition, 51% reported poor sleep quality, which affects their performance and impacts their students' results... they negatively affect their students because they create a negative environment and low student performance..."

When professors are highly stressed, their students have more difficulty adjusting socially and performing academically.” (in Delgado 2019).

The Education Support organization claims that the mental health of British professors is in such poor shape that, according to a survey of 3,082 professors, 59% are looking to leave the profession, and 78% experience symptoms of mental health problems due to their job, yet 47% still go to work (Delgado 2023). The consulting organization RAND (2022) which surveyed 2,360 professors and 1,540 head professors found that educators have worse well-being than other professions, almost three-quarters of professors and 85% of head professors said they frequently experience work-related stress, in comparison, only 44% of workers in other areas gave the same response. Another example is from Peru, where 56% of professors suffered from stress problems in 2022. The study also concluded that this is because professors have a double workload since they are expected to be in charge of their students' education, attend to their socio-emotional needs, and attend to the needs of students' families (Velásquez 2023).

All the above has meant a transformation in the profile of today's professors, regardless of age, experience, or hierarchy; and especially for engineering schools, which are involved in this conference. There is no doubt about the vocation of most engineering professors; however, designing educational models appropriate for today's students becomes a challenge that requires ongoing didactic updates in multiple aspects: assessment systems, learning styles, rubric design, ties to public and private institutions, etc. The social well-being and mental health of professors are, without a doubt, undervalued and underestimated.

These new demands of the profession are also triggering new cultural practices within the profession itself to cope with the demands of this pace of life in a healthy way and with the least possible negative impact. A faster pace of life than ever before, impacting the professional and personal spheres, as well as families and communities close to the professors.

One of the common consequences of this pace of life is burnout syndrome, which is reflected in stress, physical and mental exhaustion, decreased academic productivity and intellectual vitality, and demotivation, among other symptoms. The consequences of this syndrome gradually increase and spread to other aspects of professors' lives, impacting their physical, mental, and emotional health and calling into question their indispensable professional contribution to humanity. In this context, recreational activities for professors within the institution, such as the 1943 Club Karaoke program, which is the focus of this article, are cultural instruments that serve to prevent, avoid, and alleviate the incidence of burnout syndrome in the academic community and promote human flourishing.

The research assumption (Hernández 2018) is: “The Karaoke of Club 1943 [of the Monterrey Campus of Tecnológico de Monterrey] is a cultural instrument that fulfills a necessary function to prevent, avoid and reduce the incidence of burnout syndrome in the academic community, to promote human flourishing in its professors.”

This research has the general objective of:

To demonstrate the importance of addressing these needs to maintain faculty occupational health within a university culture, resulting in greater willingness to implement new active learning teaching techniques with engineering students. And three specific objectives

- 1) Explain why an activity like the Club 1943 Karaoke a university cultural phenomenon worthy of analysis is.
- 2) Describe how it was implemented in a large group of professors at the Tecnológico de Monterrey, Monterrey Campus.

- 3) To demonstrate why it is an innovative way to prevent, avoid, or mitigate the impact of burnout syndrome and to stimulate the professor's human flourishing.

It should be noted that the team of authors of this work, in addition to their teaching and research work, are part of the administrative team that manages and monitors the "Club 1943 Karaoke" at Monterrey Campus.

This paper will first explain how this initiative works as a university cultural phenomenon and address the importance of these initiatives considering burnout syndrome and human flourishing. It will then describe the initiative's implementation, as well as an evaluation of the results and conclusions drawn from the exercise.

2. Development

In December 2015, the professors spontaneously selected a recreational and social space with a novel element: karaoke, where singing, dancing, clapping, smiling, and eating generated a shared sense of joy and freedom. Unexpectedly, this karaoke took shape naturally and was named Club 1943 Karaoke. It is currently held monthly, attended by an average of 130 professors, and has remained active, remotely, throughout the COVID-19 pandemic.

In 2016, the 1943 Club Karaoke was established for the socializing and recreation of the teaching community. The number "1943" refers to the year the Tecnológico de Monterrey was founded, on Monday, September 6th, 82 years ago. At the initiative of the "Honors" program then directed by Dr. Liliana Manrique and with the support of Dr. Alfonso Serrano, the space was equipped one afternoon with microphones, sound equipment, and screens to foster artistic expression. Over time, this space became a model of informal and spontaneous socializing among colleagues. Initially, some colleagues timidly took the microphone to participate in these gatherings. Encouraged by the heartfelt applause, more and more colleagues gradually began to sing and dance, setting the tone for future sessions. In subsequent meetings, through a song selected individually, as a duet or as a team, this group of professors shared smiles and discovered themselves in a phenomenon that the Russian literary theorist Mikhail Bakhtin associated it with carnival: a primitive joy, a sense of brotherhood and liberation that united them as a community. Thus, the 1943 Karaoke Club was formed.

2.1 Theoretical basis of the university cultural phenomenon.

What role does the university professor play in this 21st-century educational model differ from previous periods? According to Ayala (2002), in the 21st century, the role of the traditional professor is now also that of an advisor who shows trust and respect for the diverse development possibilities of each of their students, which motivates them to seek the most effective way for them to achieve comprehensive training. Fulfilling this new attribute of the professor generates greater formative responsibility and training demands in many ways, not only in the specialized area of knowledge; faced with this additional workload, moments are required to release tension and reduce the exhaustion that this responsibility entails.

Mexican anthropologist Bonfil (1987) proposes the concept of a cultural instrument as a means of understanding a specific culture. For Bonfil, a cultural instrument is "any collective act with a common social purpose" (108) that generates identity and unity within a group, such as the phenomenon analyzed here. The types of cultural instruments Bonfil refers to are material, demographic, organizational, knowledge, symbolic and communication, and emotive or subjective. Thus, Club 19.43's karaoke is identified as a symbolic and communication cultural instrument, as it is a practice that influences integration and socialization among professors; and also an emotive or subjective type of instrument, due to the affection and friendship that are strengthened within a group, a product of the affective motivation for integration into the group that each professor integrates into this community.

With suspicious, joyful glances and sincere collusion, a group of established, new, and emeritus professors from all disciplines—researchers, established authors, and those with a variety of academic and scientific accolades—

come to the evening gathering at the Monterrey Campus. They aim to shed their intellectual prestige and become witnesses and protagonists of a carnivalesque cultural phenomenon, revealing themselves as living elements of the celebration and culture of laughter proposed by the Russian philosopher Mikhail Bakhtin (1875–1975).

In 2002, researcher Tatiyana Bubnova gave a lecture at the Monterrey Institute of Technology, Monterrey Campus, entitled "Party, Rupture and Transgression, according to Bakhtin," to explain the theoretical proposal of the Russian theorist in his work *Popular culture in the Middle Ages and the Renaissance*. According to Bubnova (2002), Bakhtin (1995) proposes reading the festivals and celebrations as a transhistorical cultural phenomenon of Humanity, whose function is to transgress the social reality of a given moment in order to confront, through catharsis and collective rejoicing, the structures and hierarchies that keep all people in certain roles, submissions, obligations, norms, silences, among many other forms of social pressure and that, as a whole, make up the entire machinery of a social structure. Thus, within an apparent sense of freedom, a moment of celebration and collective enjoyment becomes a sublime time that returns us to the liberating origin of Humanity. By human nature, primitive men and women, by identifying each other as necessary and vulnerable, when they managed to survive the uncontrollable forces of nature, formulated the need to celebrate with expressions of joy and group security through shouts, laughter, body language movements and within a collective hubbub.

This phenomenon is observed in the teaching community that attends the Club 1943 Karaoke to confront, for an afternoon and with an apparent sense of freedom, the established social order, although after that moment of liberation everything returns to normal.

2.2 Theoretical support from burnout syndrome and human flourishing

As explained above, in the current work environment, professors are overwhelmed and immersed in uncertainty, subject to constant training demands, academic and administrative requirements, and simultaneously developing research projects in their specialty and in educational innovation. In this context, teaching staff are exposed to burnout syndrome. Quirónprevención (2018) defines this syndrome as follows:

The syndrome of *Burnout*, or "burned-out worker syndrome," refers to the chronic nature of work-related stress. It manifests itself through a state of physical and mental exhaustion that lasts over time and can alter a worker's personality and self-esteem. It is a process in which workers gradually lose interest in their tasks and develop a negative psychological reaction to their job.

Causes of burnout include work overload, lack of time to complete tasks, excessive responsibilities, stress (performance demands, lack of support from superiors), lack of autonomy in one's work, lack of recognition from superiors, a negative work environment, as well as individual factors such as a tendency toward anxiety, lack of boundaries, and difficulty saying no.

The physical symptoms of this syndrome include physical exhaustion, chronic fatigue, difficulty sleeping, lack of energy, headaches, muscle tension, gastrointestinal problems, changes in appetite, and changes in the menstrual cycle.

Emotional symptoms that often manifest include a feeling of failure, disinterest in work, loss of motivation, irritability, cynicism, anger, impatience with colleagues and clients, a constant state of anxiety and nervousness, difficulty concentrating, feelings of sadness, hopelessness, loss of interest in activities, decreased self-esteem, and skepticism about one's own abilities and capabilities.

Behavioral symptoms include social and professional withdrawal, difficulty interacting, reduced productivity, procrastination, lack of attention to tasks and work commitment, and absenteeism.

Given this phenomenon in the university workplace, it is necessary to create a space for faculty members, following the theoretical proposals of Bonfil and Bakhtin, to experience a catharsis that provides a sense of liberation and shared joy, enabling the group to integrate, strengthen, and regain the prudence, energy, and good spirit to carry out their university work and thus achieve human flourishing.

For the Monterrey Institute of Technology (2024), human flourishing:

It is a personal and conscious process of developing capacities in all areas of life, in which each person relates to the community and the environment to create a better world, respecting their own dignity and that of others... [even when carried out in a community] the person is the center. It is a conscious process that responds to personal convictions, purpose, and actions. It is a process interrelated with the conditions of the social and environmental context. Human flourishing is an end in itself.

Professors must be aware of their own human flourishing to foster it in their students, integrating it into the teaching process within the university setting, that is, in the classroom or laboratory. Therefore, teaching must be complemented by the integration of cultural, cathartic, and personal harmony aspects to be able to give themselves to others, enjoying personal fulfillment in every sense.

3. Implementation of the “Club 1943 Karaoke” for the teaching community

What is karaoke? The Royal Spanish Academy defines it as: "Entertainment consisting of singing a song to a recorded musical background, while following the lyrics displayed on a screen. [It includes] the technical equipment consisting of a sound amplifier, microphone, etc., used for karaoke.

And who is the architect of this cultural phenomenon at Tec de Monterrey? The Monterrey Campus Events Management Department is responsible for Club 1943, led by Martha Maqueo until December 2024 and currently by Emma Inés Cortés, with a valuable team comprised of Alejandra Silva, Cecilia Ordaz, Jorge Tello, Marvin González, Oscar Rodríguez, and María Eugenia Morales.

First, a large, enclosed space on Monterrey Campus is selected monthly, open from 5:30 to 8:30 pm, with exclusive access for professors. Sound equipment is installed, along with a computer to connect to a karaoke website, and four microphones are set up in front of the venue, with a stage-like space. Twelve round tables, each clearly numbered from 1 to 12, are arranged, each with ten chairs. Upon arrival, each teaching assistant sits down and chats freely with their tablemates. The Club 1943 Karaoke Lead Professor brings the program and invites the tables to participate; he asks the name of the song, making humorous, upbeat comments that contribute to the integration. Each table forms a team and decides which song to perform, the musical genre, and the number of members who will appear on stage (an individual singer, a duet, or all members of the table). It's important to note that, although the current table decides which song to perform and/or dance to, the other professors at other tables are free to join them in singing or dancing, which is the case most of the time. During the three-hour event, an average of 45 songs are sung, and each table can sing four times. The Event Management Department invites guests to dinner (tamales, tacos, a buffet of casserole, hamburgers, etc.), soft drinks, beer, cake, and coffee; the amount of food is calculated from the list of professors registered for the event at least ten days in advance. The invitation is extended to the general academic community via email.

María Eugenia Morales is the Leader of the Events Management Department, which organizes graduations, degree signings, start-up and end-of-semester events, Professors' Day, etc., and thanks to what this work has demonstrated, starting in 2022, Club 1943 Karaoke has been formally integrated into the institutional events of the Monterrey Campus.

María Eugenia Morales, co-author of this work, has been with her *Alma Mater* for 34 years and has also collaborated in various venues such as the Library and the Book Fair. She states: "The purpose of the Club 1943 Karaoke is to provide the teaching community with a space for recreation and fun, something different from what is, for them, the reason they exist at Tec de Monterrey. It's extremely necessary for them to have a moment of relaxation and forget about their daily activities, de-stress, and set aside their academic pursuits to meet and socialize with colleagues from different areas." Regarding the experience of creating the Club 1943 Karaoke space, she asserts: "The truth is, it's been very well received with very good results. Many have approached us requesting its organization and inquiring about upcoming dates. We like that because it means we're doing things right by filling a necessary space, and with the exact characteristics demanded by the academic community of our campus; karaoke truly fulfills its purpose".

The results of the Club 1943 Karaoke prompted the institution's authorities to allocate the necessary budget for its monthly celebration, open to the entire teaching community, whether on a full-time or subject-based contract.

4. Evaluation of results

The methodological approach of this research was quantitative and consisted of applying a total of 1058 virtual surveys to the attending professors via institutional email, one, two, or three days after fifteen sessions of Karaoke 1943. The professors surveyed were identified by School or Faculty, and whether they had attended previously or it was their first time, and they numerically evaluated their level of satisfaction with the Club 1943 Karaoke event. To complement the qualitative research, two testimonies from ten professors were selected to illustrate the experience of their participation in the event.

Quantitative results. Fifteen feedback surveys were administered to professors after the Club 1943 Karaoke sessions held between August 2023 and March 2025.

Table 1. This table indicates the date, year, attendees, first occasion of attendance and an average evaluation of the event, following the Likert scale, where 1 corresponds to the highest degree of satisfaction and 5 to the lowest degree of satisfaction.

Table 1. List of activities

Event	Weekday	Day	Month	Year	Professors	New professors	Evaluation
Karaoke	Tuesday	15	Agost	2023	77	NA	1.24
Karaoke	Wednesday	23	Agost	2023	16	NA	1.08
Karaoke	Tuesday	12	September	2023	54	NA	1.3
Karaoke	Tuesday	3	October	2023	62	NA	1.26
Karaoke	Tuesday	7	November	2023	61	NA	1.22
Christmas party	Tuesday	5	December	2023	100	NA	1.08
Karaoke	Wednesday	21	February	2024	59	12	1.2
Karaoke	Tuesday	19	March	2024	69	12	1.2
Karaoke	Wednesday	12	June	2024	85	6	1
Karaoke	Monday	19	Agost	2024	87	11	1.1
Karaoke	Wednesday	11	September	2024	88	12	1.1
Karaoke	Friday	11	October	2024	80	7	1.2
Karaoke	Monday	11	November	2024	92	8	1.1
Christmas party	Tuesday	3	December	2024	135	18	1.1
Karaoke	Monday	10	March	2025	80	6	1.1

Feedback surveys were conducted on these fifteen occasions, one day after each Karaoke 19.43 event. The number of participants varied, most likely due to the time of year at which the event was held. The overall evaluation of the event, considering the time, location, food, and atmosphere, averaged 1.15 on a Likert scale, where 1 corresponds to the highest level of satisfaction and 5 to the lowest level of satisfaction.

Table 2. This table shows the attendance of professors to the Karaoke Club1943 initiative, based on the surveys answered during the period 2023-2025, indicated by gender, as well as the number of professors in the School of Engineering.

Tabel 2. Attendance

Professors	Aug to Dec 2023	2024	Until March 2025
Women	110 = 53%	123 = 49.80%	40 = 50%
Men	98 = 47%	124 = 50.20%	40 = 50%
Total Professors	208 = 100%	247 = 100%	80 = 100%
Professors of the engineering school	91 = 43%	89 = 36%	36 = 44%

Interpretation. Table 2. Gender equity in attendance at this initiative is very evident, validating it as a need for the academic community. The average attendance rate for faculty members at the School of Engineering is 41 percent, the highest among all schools.

Table 3 shows the information from the different Academic Departments of the Monterrey Campus of those who regularly attend Club 1943 Karaoke.

Table 3. Academic departments

Period	From how many academic departments did the professors attend on Monterrey Campus?
From August to December 2023	Professors from 40 different Academic Departments
Year 2024	Professors from 50 different Academic Departments
From January to March 2025	Professors from 36 different Academic Departments

Interpretation: The Club 1943 Karaoke teaching performance initiative has impacted on the entire academic community of Monterrey Campus since professors from

Qualitative results are represented by two testimonies:

X1, professor at the engineering school, affiliated with the Women in Science initiative, member of the National System of Researchers, winner of the Tec Women's Award, and Full Professor, offered her testimony in an interview, in which she stated:

For me, [Club 1943 Karaoke] is a space for relaxation and socializing with colleagues from different schools in a healthy, friendly environment... My [work] hours are very long, and going in the afternoon seemed impossible, but when I went [to karaoke], I was captivated by the healthy, friendly atmosphere, because everyone is welcomed and there's a lot of empathy. So, thank you very much and congratulations to the organizers, they're great!

- What do you consider to be its function? -:

Foster bonds of empathy, solidarity, and friendship beyond the classroom.

- And how do you see Club 1943 in three years' time?

With greater institutional recognition, where resources are provided so that more and more colleagues become aware of it and have access to activities that promote holistic well-being.

X2, Chemical Engineer and professor at the School of Engineering and Sciences, states:

For me, Club 1943 Karaoke is a space to socialize with other professors, dancing, and sharing the joy of life. I'm not a good singer, so I prefer to enjoy other classmates' singing, and even better, when the song is right, to dance together with other colleagues. I believe that karaoke is essential in the university environment at Tec de Monterrey, as an outlet for the stress we experience as professors and for creating a unique atmosphere of camaraderie that allows us to fully enjoy these moments. All of our karaoke sessions are very enjoyable, but I especially like the ones in December because we share a video of everything we've experienced and enjoyed throughout the year. And at the end, we sing Christmas carols together and wish each other Happy Holidays.

- And how do you see Club 1943 in three years' time?

I'm sure Club 1943 will continue in the future and that more and more professors will join events like karaoke. Many thanks to the organizers of the Club 1943 events for giving us the opportunity to have these wonderful get-togethers at Tec of Monterrey.

5. Conclusions

Throughout this study, the value of Club 1943 Karaoke was confirmed as a cultural instrument that serves to prevent, avoid, and alleviate the incidence of burnout syndrome in the academic community of Tecnológico de Monterrey, especially among professors in the School of Engineering and Sciences, as well as promoting the human flourishing of the academic community. Likewise, the fulfillment of the objectives set forth at the beginning of this work is observed. Particularly noteworthy is that during the period covered by this research on the impact of Club 1943 Karaoke on professors at Monterrey Campus, 40 percent of whom are from the Engineering School and are the faculty with the greatest presence. The remaining 60 percent are distributed among more than seven schools, which is evidence of the need that this monthly event meets among this entire group of professors.

Given the experience and lessons learned over the nearly ten years of this initiative, as well as the significant impact it has had on the teaching community, academic authorities at other universities are invited to consider and value it in the same way, benefiting the physical and emotional health of their faculty members. This benefit will greatly impact and be reflected in the effectiveness of the teaching/learning processes carried out by faculty members, as well as in encouraging the development of competencies in their students. Allocating a budget, time, and space for a university cultural instrument such as the one described is an investment with benefits for the occupational health of the community, for combating burnout syndrome, and for stimulating faculty development, which is reflected in teaching practice, in the eyes of the student community, and in society at large.

The research assumption was verified: "The Club 1943 Karaoke [at the Monterrey Campus of Tecnológico de Monterrey] is a cultural instrument that fulfills a necessary function to prevent, avoid, and reduce the incidence of burnout syndrome in the academic community, to promote human flourishing in its professors " and the general objective was achieved: To demonstrate the importance of addressing these needs to take care of the occupational health of the professor within a university culture, so that it results in a greater willingness to implement new active learning didactic techniques in engineering students. And also, the three specific objectives: 1) Explain why an activity like the Club 1943 Karaoke a university cultural phenomenon worthy of

analysis is. 2) Describe how it was implemented in a large group of professors at Tecnológico de Monterrey, Monterrey Campus; and 3) Show why it is an innovative way to prevent, avoid, or alleviate the impact of burnout syndrome and stimulate the human flourishing of the professor.

The implications of this research for higher education in engineering are highly likely due to the benefits of human flourishing in the development of professional professors. Given the importance of physical and emotional health in the teaching and development processes, as well as in the development of competencies, active learning will be better implemented in daily teaching activities. It is asserted that a stress-free professor who manages to confront burnout syndrome and develop their human flourishing will be a better engineering professor, will identify with a sense of community and a shared teaching vocation, and will be a fully fulfilled individual.

Acknowledgments

To Dr. Mario Adrián Flores Castro, Vice President of the Monterrey Campus and Vice President of the Monterrey Region of Tecnológico de Monterrey, for his support for the Club 1943 monthly Karaoke celebration.

To Emma Cortés, Director of Academic Quality at Monterrey Campus, for her support in the monthly karaoke of Club 1943.

To Martha Maqueo, Director of Academic Quality at Monterrey Campus, for her support in the monthly implementation of Club 1943 Karaoke from its inception in 2016 until 2024.

References

- AI Overview (2025) Burnout syndrome. Retrieved April 21, 2025: https://www.google.com/search?q=s%C3%ADndrome+de+burnout+symptoms&rlz=1C1GCGA_enMX1085M_1085_ABBFGDkyCAGBEAAYFhgeMgglAhAAGBYHjllCAMQABgWGB4yCAGEEAAYFhgeMgglBRAAGBYHjllCAYQABgWGB4yCAGHEAAYFhgeMgglCBAAGBYHjllCAKQABgWGB7SAQqzNTkxajBqN6gCALACAA&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8.
- Ayala, F. (2002). *The professor as advisor*. Mexico: Trillas.
- Bubnova T. (2002) "Party, Rupture, and Transgression According to Bakhtin" in *Languages of Popular Tradition: Party, Song, Music, and Performance*. Jiménez de Báez, Y., Editor. El Colegio de México. Pp. 417:432. ISBN 968-12-1061-1
- Bakhtin, M. (1995). *Popular culture in the Middle Ages and the Renaissance. The context of François Rabelais*. Translated by Julio Forcat and César Conroy, Madrid: Alianza.
- Bonfil, G. (1987). "Indigenous Peoples, Their Cultures, and Cultural Policies" in García Canclini, ed. *Cultural Policies in Latin America, Mexico, Grijalbo*. Pp. 90–126
- Cultura/UNAM (2023). <https://cultura.unam.mx/evento/tiempos-modernos>. Retrieved April 21, 2025.
- Delgado, P. (2019). "Educators also need support to manage their stress." *EduNews*. Observatory of Educational Innovation. Tecnológico de Monterrey. November 4, 2019. <https://observatorio.tec.mx/salud-mental-docentes/> Retrieved May 30, 2025.
- García, D. (2022). "Burnout at work: what it is and how to prevent work from overwhelming you." *Conecta*. News site of the Tecnológico de Monterrey. November 30, 2022. <https://conecta.tec.mx/es/noticias/nacional/salud/burnout-laboral> Retrieved May 30, 2025.
- Hernández, R. (2018). *Research Methodology. The Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Routes*. Mexico City, Mexico: Editorial Mc Graw Hill Education.
- RAND. (2022). "Restoring Professor and Principal Well-Being Is an Essential Step for Rebuilding Schools." June 15, 2023. RAND.ORG. https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RRA1108-4.html Retrieved May 30, 2025.
- Monterrey Institute of Technology. (2024). *Environment for Flourishing*. Monterrey Institute of Technology <https://tec.mx/es/floreCIMIENTO-humano/entorno-para-floreCER>. Retrieved April 22, 2025
- Torres, M. (2023). "Work-related stress in the teaching profession: identify it and avoid risks." *Conecta*. News site of the Tecnológico de Monterrey. July 25, 2023. <https://conecta.tec.mx/es/noticias/nacional/salud/estres-laboral-en-la-profesion-docente-identificalo-y-evita-riesgos>. Retrieved May 30, 2025.
- UNAM (2023). "Mexico: Alarming Workplace Stress Figures." *UNAM Global Magazine*. April 30, 2023. Retrieved May 30, 2025: https://unamglobal.unam.mx/global_revista/mexico-alarman-tes-cifras-de-estres-laboral/
- Quironprevencion (2018) *Burnout syndrome*. <https://www.quironprevencion.com/blogs/es/prevenidos/sintomas-sindrome-burnout-identificadorlo>. Retrieved April 21, 2025
- Velásquez, A. (2023). "Mental Health: 55.8% of professors suffered from stress problems in the second year of the pandemic". Report. Pulso PUCP. Pontifical Catholic University of Peru. March 3, 2023. Retrieved May 30, 2025: <https://pulso.pucp.edu.pe/noticias/salud-mental-el-55-8-de-docentes-padecio-problemas-de-estres-en-el-segundo-ano-de-la-pandemia>